

Effect of Education Using Animation on the Ability to Develop Personal Skills for Early Stroke Detection and Initial Treatment at Home

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Abstract

Background: The success of stroke treatment depends on the speed and accuracy of early detection and prompt transportation to health facilities. However, many people have not received information on how to detect and treat the condition at home.

Objective: The aim is to determine the effect of education using animation on the ability to develop personal skills for early stroke detection and initial treatment at home in Kupang City.

Methodology: The research method used a quasi-experimental design with a quota sampling technique, involving two groups: intervention and control. The intervention group received education through animated videos, while the control group did not. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire to identify the knowledge and skills of early stroke detection. Data were analysed using the chi-square test and logistic regression.

Results: The results of the logistic regression test obtained a knowledge value of $0.222 > 0.05$ (alpha) so that there was no effect of education using animation on knowledge for early detection

of stroke attacks and initial handling at home, but on the skill variable obtained a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$ (alpha) so that there was an effect of education using animation on the ability to develop personal skills on skills for early detection of stroke attacks and initial handling at home. The model summary obtained a Nagelkerke R Square value of 0.360, which means that the intervention contributed 36% to improving skills, while different variables contributed 64%. Variables in the Equation obtained an Exp(B) value of 14.7, meaning respondents who receive the intervention are 14.7 times more likely to experience skill improvement.

Conclusion: This study's findings illustrate the use of animated media in health education programmes according to the community's needs.

Unique Contribution: This study introduces animated videos as an innovative educational medium to improve stroke early detection skills. The results provide further exploration opportunities for the long-term impact of animation-based education, especially in terms of the sustainability of stroke detection and early response skills at the community level.

Key recommendation: Educational animated videos must be integrated into community health promotion programmes, adapting to the local cultural context. Further research is needed on audiovisual media integration and community-based approaches to improving personal skills for the early detection of stroke.

Keywords: Animation, Early stroke detection, Pre-hospital

Introduction

Stroke is the second leading cause of death in the world and the third leading cause of death and disability. Every year, 15 million people worldwide suffer a stroke. Of these, 5 million die, and another 5 million are permanently disabled, placing a burden on families and society (WHO, 2022). In Indonesia, stroke is ranked as the first cause of death, with a prevalence that continues to increase as the population ages and lifestyle changes (Risksedas, 2019).

In East Nusa Tenggara in Indonesia, the highest stroke incidence rates were in Sikka (9%), Kupang (5%), East Flores (7%), Manggarai (8%), and Central Sumba (5%) (Risksedas, 2019). Risk factors for stroke are poor stress management, diet, lifestyle, physical activity, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus. Stroke attacks must be treated immediately to reduce complications, aggravating the patient's condition. Early detection of stroke attacks is carried out before the patient is taken to the nearest health service. Families need to know this action well. The form of early detection that needs to be understood by the community is using the FAST (Face, Arm, Speech, Time) approach. FAST is important in helping individuals recognise stroke emergencies. Early treatment before bringing the patient down to the hospital will be decisive in improving the patient's condition and prognosis (Aty, 2023). In this context, using animation as an instructional tool can significantly improve public knowledge of the condition. The strategy presents facts in an interesting and easy-to-understand fashion, making it more successful in transmitting concepts (Cahyadi, 2019).

A study conducted on 10 families with stroke patients in Kupang City revealed that the respondents lacked an understanding of the early symptoms of stroke. The family panicked and did not immediately take the patient to the hospital when the condition occurred. A previous study also showed that the primary factor affecting Pre-Hospital Stroke Management in Kupang City, using

logistic regression analysis, was when the family decided to take the patient to the hospital. Meanwhile, knowledge, public beliefs, and perceptions of stroke management did not affect the accuracy of pre-hospital patient management (Bita Aty et al., 2024).

Several studies have shown that the most common signs and symptoms of stroke are sudden weakness or numbness of the face, arms, or legs, often on one side of the body (Phipps & Cronin, 2020). Others include confusion, difficulty in speaking, understanding speech, seeing, walking, dizziness, loss of balance, severe headaches without known cause, fainting, or unconsciousness. These symptoms need to be known by the family and patient for effective management (Rondonuwu, 2019).

The success of stroke management is dependent on the ability of the surrounding people or family to recognise early symptoms and seek medical help (Muskananfolo et al., 2021). Medical practitioners also need to quickly diagnose or conduct examinations as well as provide appropriate management within a maximum of 6 hours (Septiana et al., 2020). Early detection and identification can be carried out as an initial effort to help people make decisions and seek health assistance quickly to prevent worsening signs of stroke (Setianingsih, 2019). The success of treatment depends on the speed and accuracy of early detection, transportation to the nearest healthcare facility, evaluation or diagnosis, and adequate emergency treatment in the hospital (Setianingsih et al., 2019)..

The cause of the delay in handling is due to the time-consuming process of family decision-making, coordination, communication, and the lack of empowerment of health facilities (Rosmary & Handayani, 2020). Other problems often found in the public are attitudes, behaviour, and low levels of education (Sari & Yuliano, 2019). Consequently, the Indonesian Ministry of Health has developed an early stroke detection method easily followed by the public using the slogan "SeGeRa Ke RS" (Kemenkes RI, 2018). The programme has been implemented for 5 years, but many people have not been exposed to the information. This is evidenced by the results of an initial survey conducted on 20 respondents with families of stroke sufferers in Kupang City who did not know the early symptoms.

According to previous studies, audiovisual media can increase knowledge because they attract and direct attention and concentration to the material, stimulate emotions and attitudes, and make it easy to remember the information or messages conveyed. Audiovisual media used by the public today are mostly contained in social media, such as YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and others (Leonita & Jalinus, 2018).

In Kupang City, various government information and programmes on health have not been realised properly and are not widely known by the public (Ajinegoro & Kurniawan, 2023). One advantage of using animation in education is its ability to arouse emotions and attract the attention of the audience. By presenting information visually, animation can create a more interactive and enjoyable learning experience (Cahyadi, 2019).

Developing personal skills is also an important part of early stroke detection. The capacity to detect stroke signs, make appropriate decisions, and conduct first-aid procedures might boost people's confidence in dealing with situations (Kaur et al., 2022). Respondents are anticipated to learn the

abilities required to detect and treat stroke efficiently after incorporating animation teaching into the training curriculum.

Various efforts have been made to improve family knowledge about early stroke detection. This study applies audiovisual media to improve the ability to develop personal skills for early stroke detection. The aim is to determine the Effect of Education Using Animation on the Ability to Develop Personal Skills for Early Stroke Detection and Initial Treatment at Home in Kupang City. This study hypothesises that education using animation significantly affects the ability to develop personal skills for early detection of stroke attacks and handling at home.

Study Methodology and Design

This study was quantitative and quasi-experimental, comparing the intervention results of the experimental and control groups. The target population was families with stroke risk in Kupang City, and the minimum number of samples required was 30 people. Therefore, a total of 30 respondents for the control and intervention groups were used in this study.

The sample inclusion criteria included families with members at risk of stroke (DM, severe hypertension sufferers), aged 17-50, mentally and physically healthy, while the exclusion criteria were respondents who did not use social media applications. The technique used in this study was non-probability sampling, namely, sample selection with Quota sampling. The independent variable was education using animation media, and the dependent variable was the early detection behaviour of stroke attacks.

Data collection

The data collection process began after the respondents signed the consent form, and the authors began collecting data according to the study method, which started with a pre-test. After the pre-test was carried out, the researcher sent the YouTube link <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k9ZCocNUf6E> to the respondents of the video via WhatsApp to their mobile phones as material to be studied and applied independently. Respondents were allowed to watch this video 4 times a week for one month. During the research process, the researcher continued to monitor the respondents' activities to view the animated video through home visits and through WhatsApp messages. For a month, the authors continued to monitor the respondents' activities by watching the video, and the control group was not given any intervention. After the treatment was completed in a month, the authors redistributed the questionnaire to be filled out by the respondents to find out when there was an effect after the treatment was given, which was conducted from May to June 2024.

Study instrument

This study used a questionnaire consisting of 3 parts, which included Questionnaire A containing the characteristics of the respondents and 4 interview questions about the experience in assisting stroke patients. Questionnaire B measured the respondents' knowledge about early stroke detection and treatment, with a total of 12 questions. Correct answers were scored 1, and incorrect answers were scored 2, hence, the highest score was 12, and the lowest was 0. Questionnaire C focused on stroke management skills and consisted of 16 Guttman scale statements. On this scale, when the respondent answered, "strongly agree," a score of 4 was given, "agree" was scored 3, "less agree" was scored 2, and "disagree" was scored 1. The highest score for this section was 64, and the lowest

was 16. Other instruments used in this study were booklets and animation videos about early detection and treatment of pre-hospital stroke. The validity test was conducted at the Baumata Public Health Centre, located 10-15 km from the location, involving 10 respondents who met the inclusion criteria. The validity test results, with a significance level of $\alpha = 5\%$, showed that questions 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 17, 18, 19, and 20 were valid. Meanwhile, questions 2, 12, 15, and 16 were invalid and were replaced with different questions. The reliability test result showed that the overall r count (Cronbach's alpha) value was 0.763, greater than the r table of 0.632, and based on the significance level of $\alpha = 5\%$, the questionnaire was reliable and consistent.

Data Analysis

In this study, data analysis was carried out using appropriate statistical methods to measure the effect of education provided through animation media on the ability to develop personal skills in early stroke detection and treatment in Kupang City. A total of 2 analysis techniques were used namely bivariate analysis with Chi-Square. After conducting this study, it continued with **logistic regression** to analyse the effect of education using animation on the ability to develop personal skills.

The study ethics board could conduct ethical testing at the Health Polytechnic (Poltekkes) of the Ministry of Health (Kemenkes), Kupang. The number decree of the 2024 Ethical Test results was No.LB.02.03/1/0237/2024. The writers also protected the right to confidentiality and anonymity. The study was entirely voluntary, and withdrawal was accepted with no consequences. All respondents provided written agreement, and only the authors and independent coders had access to the data that was gathered.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Respondents' Characteristics Based on Gender, Age, Education Level and Occupation

Variable	Intervention	%	Control	%
Gender				
Male	17	57	18	60
Female	13	43	12	40
Total	30	100	30	100
Age				0
10-18 years old		0	1	3
19-59 years old	19	63	29	97
60-75 years old	11	37		
Total	30	100	30	100
Education Level		0		0
Elementary School	9	30	4	13
Junior High School	4	13		0
Senior High School	9	30	18	60
Diploma/Bachelor's Degree	8	27	8	27
Total	30	100	30	100
Occupation		0		0
Civil Servant/Police/TNI (Indonesian Army)	3	10	4	13

Teacher	1	3	3	10
Self-Employed		0	2	7
Non-Civil Servant	10	33	14	47
Housewife	16	53	7	23
Total	30	100	30	100

Table 1 revealed that the number of respondents was 60, which was divided into 30 in both the control and intervention groups. Most respondents in both groups were male, with a percentage of 57% in the intervention and 60% in the control group. The age of the majority in both groups ranged from 19 to 59 years, with 63% in the intervention and 97% in the control group. Most education levels were senior high school, namely 30% and 60% in both groups. In addition, most respondents in the control group worked as housewives (53%), while in the intervention, the majority worked as non-Civil Servant workers (47).

Table 2. Ability to Develop Personal Skills: Knowledge and Skills for Early Stroke Detection and Initial Treatment Before Being Given Animation Videos

Pre Knowledge Category		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Good	33	55.0
	Adequate	26	43.3
	Poor	1	1.7
	Total	60	100.0
Pre Skills Category		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Good	3	5.0
	Adequate	56	93.3
	Poor	1	1.7
	Total	60	100.0

Table 2 showed that 33 people (55%) had good knowledge before the intervention, 26 were adequate (43.3%), and only 1 was poor (1.7%). The table also indicated that 3 people (5%) had good skills before the intervention, 56 were adequate (93.3%), and only 1 was poor (1.7%).

Table 3. Analysis of the Ability to Develop Personal Skills: Knowledge and Skills for Early Stroke Detection and Initial Before Being Given Animation Videos

Group * Pre Knowledge Category Crosstabulation						
			Pre Knowledge Category			Total
			Good	Adequate	Poor	
Group	Intervention	Count	16	13	1	30
		% of Total	26.7%	21.7%	1.7%	50.0%
	Control	Count	17	13	0	30
		% of Total	28.3%	21.7%	0.0%	50.0%
Total		Count	33	26	1	60
		% of Total	55.0%	43.3%	1.7%	100.0%
Group * Pre Skills Category Crosstabulation						
			Pre Skills Category			Total
			Good	Adequate	Poor	
Group	Intervention	Count	3	27	0	30
		% of Total	5.0%	45.0%	0.0%	50.0%
	Control	Count	0	29	1	30
		% of Total	0.0%	48.3%	3.3%	51.7%

		% of Total	0.0%	48.3%	1.7%	50.0%
Total	Count		3	56	1	60
	% of Total		5.0%	93.3%	1.7%	100.0%

Based on Table 3, in the intervention group, the number of respondents with good pre-knowledge was 16 people (26.7%), followed by 13 people (21.7%) with adequate pre-knowledge and 1 person (1.7%) with poor pre-knowledge, which was relatively not much different. The number of respondents with good pre-knowledge was 17 people (28.3%), followed by 13 people (21.7%) with adequate pre-knowledge, and no respondents had poor knowledge. The table above also showed that, in the intervention group, the number of respondents with good pre-skills was 3 people (5%), 27 people were adequate (45%), and none had poor skills. In the control group, it was relatively not much different, where the number of respondents with good pre-skills was none, 29 people were adequate (48.3%), and only 1 respondent had poor skills (1.7%).

Table 4. Identifying the Ability to Develop Personal Skills: Knowledge and Skills for Early Stroke Detection and Initial Treatment After Being Given Animation Videos

Post Knowledge Category		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Good	51	85.0
	Adequate	9	15.0
	Total	60	100.0
Post Skill Category		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Good	18	30.0
	Adequate	42	70.0
	Total	60	100.0

Based on Table 4, 51 people (85%) had good knowledge after the intervention, 9 were adequate (15%), and none were poor. In addition, it also showed that 18 people (30%) had good skills after the intervention, 42 were adequate (70%), and none were poor.

Table 5. Analysis of the Ability to Develop Personal Skills: Knowledge and Skills for Early Stroke Detection and Initial Treatment after Being Given Animation Videos

Group * Post Knowledge Category Crosstabulation			Post Knowledge Category		Total
			Good	Adequate	
Group	Intervention	Count	28	2	30
		% of Total	46.7%	3.3%	50.0%
	Control	Count	23	7	30
		% of Total	38.3%	11.7%	50.0%
Total		Count	51	9	60
		% of Total	85.0%	15.0%	100.0%
Group * Post Skills Category Crosstabulation			Post Skill Category		Total
			Good	Adequate	
Group	Intervention	Count	16	14	30
		% of Total	26.7%	23.3%	50.0%
	Control	Count	2	28	30
		% of Total	3.3%	46.7%	50.0%
Total		Count	18	42	60
		% of Total	30.0%	70.0%	100.0%

In the Table 5, the number of respondents with good knowledge was 28 people (46.7%), 2 people (3.3%) were adequate, and none were poor. In the control group, it was slightly different. The number of respondents with good knowledge was 23 people (38.3%), adequate were 7 people

(11.7%), and none had poor knowledge. In addition, it also indicated that, in the intervention group, the number of respondents with good skills was 16 people (27.7%), 14 were adequate (23.3%), and none were poor. In the control group, it was very different where the number of respondents with good skills after the intervention was 2 people (3.3%), adequate were 28 people (46.7%), and none were poor.

Table 6. The Effect of Education Using Animation on the Ability to Develop Personal Skills for Early Stroke Detection and Initial Treatment at Home

Model Summary									
Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square						
1	64.318 ^a	.270	.360						
a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 5 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.									
Variables in the Equation									
		B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
								Lower	Upper
Step 1 ^a	Knowledge_Post_Kat	1.159	.948	1.495	1	.222	3.186	.497	20.418
	Skills_Post_Kat	2.688	.825	10.602	1	.001	14.700	2.915	74.124
	Constant	-6.022	1.868	10.391	1	.001	.002		
a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: Knowledge_Post_Kat, Skills_Post_Kat.									

No	Variable Name	P value	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	Knowledge	0.222	0.270	0.360
2	Skills	0.001		

Logistic Regression Analysis:

- a. Based on the analysis results using the Logistic Regression Test, the significance value of knowledge was $0.222 > 0.05$ (alpha). Therefore, it could be concluded that there was no Effect of Education Using Animation on the Ability to Develop Personal Skills at the knowledge point for Early Stroke Detection and Initial Treatment at Home.
- b. This was different from the analysis results on the skills variable using the Logistic Regression Test, and the significance value of skills was $0.001 < 0.05$ (alpha). Therefore, it could be concluded that there was an Effect of Education Using Animation on the Ability to Develop Personal Skills at the skill point for Early Stroke Detection and Initial Treatment at Home.
- c. Based on the Model Summary table, the Nagelkerke R Square value showing the contribution of the intervention variable to skills was 0.360. This meant that the intervention contributed 36% to improving skills, while 64% was affected by other variables.
- d. In the Variables in the Equation table in the logistic regression analysis, the Exp (B) value was 14.7. This meant that respondents receiving the intervention were 14.7 times more likely to experience increased skills.

The results showed that there were differences between the intervention group and the control group about knowledge and skills before the educational intervention. The knowledge aspect of

respondents in both the intervention and control groups was good and sufficient. In terms of skills, there was a more significant difference where the control group showed lower skills than the intervention group.

Before the intervention, 26.7% of respondents in the intervention group and 28.3% in the control group had a good level of knowledge. This shows that in both groups, most respondents already had a sufficient knowledge base about early stroke detection and early pre-hospital care. However, although the difference was small, the intervention group was slightly behind in terms of knowledge before the intervention. This finding was relevant to Li et al. (2019) that the level of basic public knowledge about cardiovascular disease, including stroke, was still less than optimal in many areas, especially those related to early signs of stroke. This factor was often related to a lack of access to easily understood sources of information, including low health literacy.

Another study (Han and Jang, 2021) also showed that health education focusing on the signs and symptoms of stroke needed to be intensified through various media, especially in the community environment. More interesting results were found in the skills variable, and in the intervention group, only 5% of respondents had good skills, most (45%) had adequate skills. In the control group, 1.7% had poor skills. Skills in handling emergencies such as stroke at home required training and simulation, not just theoretical knowledge (Widyanto et al., 2022). Practical skills in handling stroke independently at home were crucial, especially in environments with limited access to health facilities. These abilities were more difficult to obtain than knowledge since they required practical experience and were rarely taught explicitly in public health education programs. Health education that incorporated visual media or simulations, such as animation, has a large potential to increase practical abilities (Kononowicz et al., 2019).

The study also emphasised the relevance of skills training via interactive methods, finding that simulation-based training might considerably improve responders' capacity to handle emergency situations. This study hypothesised that animation-based instructional interventions would improve learning outcomes.

The study also found a gap in knowledge and ability. This was consistent with the learning theory, which states that theoretical knowledge is not always exactly proportionate to practical skills. Knowledge might be received from different sources, but without supporting practical exercises, abilities were difficult to develop (Septi et al., 2022).

Stated that interventions based on audiovisual media could also help improve respondents' skills. Media such as animation could reduce the cognitive load in absorbing complex information due to its clearer visual representation. According to Desyani et al. (2024) interventions focussing on audiovisual media may also help respondents improve their skills. Because of its clearer visual representation, media like animation may reduce the cognitive strain associated with digesting complex information. As a result, animation-based intervention tactics have the potential to greatly improve responders' practical skills in diagnosing and treating strokes.

Based on the findings above, although most respondents had an adequately good level of knowledge before the intervention, their practical skills were still low, especially in the control group. This

emphasised the importance of providing education focusing not only on knowledge but also on practical skills. Education using animation was an effective method to bridge this gap, as supported by previous studies that interactive visualisation could significantly improve practical skills.

The significantly enhanced knowledge in the intervention group demonstrated that interactive instructional media had a beneficial effect. This was consistent with Aisah et al., (2021), who found that visual strategies could boost knowledge absorption more effectively than traditional means such as lectures or brochures. Animation videos allowed viewers to replay poorly understood content, thereby giving flexibility in the learning process.

The use of these animation videos was preferred because it was attractive in terms of appearance and had an interesting sound. However, respondents found it easier to understand the information provided and felt happy during the knowledge transfer process.

Animation videos that often contain interactive simulations could provide a more in-depth learning experience (Rofiqoh & Khairani, 2024). A person's skills in dealing with emergencies were greatly affected by the frequency of exposure and repeated practice. One source of learning for this exercise was animation videos that could be accessed via YouTube and other social media. Respondents could see practical steps in dealing with stroke, therefore increasing their readiness to apply this knowledge in real life.

Terndrup et al. (2013) stated that short animation videos were easy for viewers to follow. When this was performed continuously, it improved cognitive and motor skills by visualising the steps in handling an emergency. In the context of stroke management, the ability to recognize early signs and take quick action could save lives, indicating the importance of improving the skills acquired through this educational intervention.

The control group also experienced an increase in knowledge and skills, but the results were much lower than those of the intervention group. Only 3.3% of respondents in the control group had good skills, indicating that conventional education methods were less effective in developing practical skills needed in emergencies. These results were in line with the findings of Mardian et al., (2022) that traditional health education approaches, such as lectures or one-way counseling, often did not provide significant improvements in skills. The lecture method caused the audience to get bored quickly. However, the information received could not be absorbed properly. Meanwhile, audiovisual media attracted more attention and interest from students in obtaining information.

The results of the logistic regression test analysis conducted in this study showed 2 important findings related to the effect of education using animation on the ability to develop personal skills for early stroke detection and initial treatment at home. The first finding was related to respondent knowledge, where a significance value of 0.222 (>0.05) indicated no significant effect of animation-based education on increasing knowledge. The second finding showed that the significant value on skills was 0.001 (<0.05), suggesting that animation-based education significantly increased respondent skills.

According to Praveen and Srinivasan, (2022) although animation could simplify complex information, the audience's ability to absorb and understand the information was still affected by other factors, such as education level, cultural background, and individual motivation to learn. Moreover, a single delivery method, such as animation videos, could not be effective enough to increase knowledge, especially when it was not complemented by a more interactive approach, such as group discussions or live Q and A sessions.

In the context of stroke knowledge, animation-based education could increase understanding. However, obtaining significant changes in the level of knowledge often required repetition of information and continuous delivery. This could explain why single animation education did not provide substantial results on the knowledge aspect of this study.

The analysis results showed that animation-based education significantly affected early stroke detection and treatment skills. A significance value of 0.001 indicated that respondents who received animation intervention experienced a better increase in skills than the control group. Furthermore, the Nagelkerke R Square value of 0.360 suggested that the intervention variable contributed 36% to the increase in skills. In comparison, the other 64% was affected by other factors not examined in this study. Learning through technology could replace face-to-face training, making it more effective and efficient (Francis et al., 2020; Khalidiyah, 2015).

The findings of this study have substantial implications for attempts to improve public health education, particularly in terms of early stroke detection and treatment. Animation-based instruction improved respondents' practical abilities and proved critical in the treatment of stroke attacks. Therefore, health education programmes for the public must consider the use of animation media as an essential tool in skills training.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study found that animation-based instruction had a substantial impact on early stroke diagnosis and treatment skills, but not on knowledge. Therefore, animation as an educational medium could be integrated into a broader health training programme to ensure the public has adequate practical skills in dealing with emergencies such as stroke.

Acknowledgements

The authors were grateful to the respondents, the team, the director of The Health Polytechnic (Poltekkes) of the Ministry of Health (Kemenkes) Kupang, family and friends for their support in this study. Hopefully, the results could be useful for the public as well as contribute positively to early stroke detection and treatment.

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